

Appendix 6 Task Force DEI Listening Session Materials

Item	Description	Page
Document 1	DEI Listening Session Announcement to Black or African American AMIA Members	2-3
Document 2	DEI Listening Session Announcement to Hispanic/Latinx AMIA Members	4-5
Document 3	Listening Session Materials for Black or African American AMIA Member Group	6-26
Document 4	Listening Session Materials for Hispanic/Latinx AMIA Member Group	27-44
Table 1	Listening Session (LS) Findings	45-51

Attachment 1. DEI Listening Session Announcement to Black or African American AMIA Members

Dear AMIA Members,

When the Diversity, Equity and Inclusion Task Force (DEI) was formed last year we knew that we would need to collect data for a baseline on where AMIA stands as an organization and individually as members. Listening sessions are an important part of our collection efforts.

We are collecting data on race, ethnicity and gender in membership demographics. The task force has also completed an environmental scan of other membership organizations in

the health and healthcare space to understand the relevant DEI work already being done and identify potential sources for learning and collaboration.

We Hear You. We Are Listening.

In February, the DEI Task Force begins hosting affinity group listening sessions (small focus groups) as part of our data gathering efforts. They will continue on a rolling basis to capture multiple identity groups. Listening sessions are just the beginning. The DEI Task Force will be launching a survey for members, former members, and non-members later this summer to catch more voices.

We are seeking 5 - 7 individuals representing a mix of professional backgrounds and a variety of experiences with AMIA. The final composition of the group will be balanced.

Participation in this session will involve answering questions about experiences as an AMIA member and an informatics professional. We hope that our findings will elucidate challenges faced by minoritized, marginalized informatics professionals and ways that AMIA can improve to become a leader in DEI efforts for informatics.

Listening Session #1

Participants: AMIA Members identifying as Black, African-American and African descent.

Date: Wednesday, February 24, 12:00 p.m. - 1:15 p.m.

Yes, I'm interested in participating: [Click here to apply for consideration.](#)

Why Are Listening Sessions Important?

The DEI Task Force is hosting listening sessions to help make recommendations to the AMIA Board of Directors on how to combat racism, sexism, ableism, LGBTQIA+-phobia and other forms of discrimination in informatics, from training

to professional practice, and within AMIA to make substantive, sustainable changes within our profession. The session is designed to create a safe place for members to share as much detail as one feels comfortable sharing. **Anything disclosed during the sessions will be strictly confidential and comments will not be directly attributed to individuals.**

Listening Session #1 will be conducted by DEI Task Force members:

- **David K. Butler, MD, FAMIA**
Calyx Healthcare Partners
- **Hope Gray, MTS, RBC**
PhD Student, Health Administration Services/Health Informatics
University of Alabama at Birmingham

Look for information soon on additional listening sessions.

Sincerely,

Tiffani J. Bright, PhD, FACMI

tiffani.bright@gmail.com | [@doc_b_right](#)

Chair, AMIA DEI Task Force

Biomedical Informatician Evaluation Team Lead

IBM Center for AI, Research, and Evaluation (CARE)

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Attachment 2. DEI Listening Session Announcement to Hispanic/Latinx AMIA Members

We Hear You. We Are Listening.

The Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (DEI) Task Force is hosting affinity group listening sessions (small focus groups) as part of the data gathering efforts. We are seeking 5 - 7 individuals representing a mix of professional backgrounds and a variety of experiences with AMIA. The final composition of the group will be balanced.

Participation in this session will involve answering questions about experiences as an AMIA member and an informatics professional. We hope that our findings will elucidate challenges faced by minoritized, marginalized informatics professionals and ways that AMIA can improve to become a leader in DEI efforts for informatics.

Listening Session #2

Participants: AMIA Members identifying as Hispanic/Latinx descent (of any race).

Date: Tuesday, March 16, 12:00 p.m. – 1:15 p.m ET

Yes, I'm interested in participating: [Click here to apply for consideration.](#)

Deadline to apply: Tuesday, March 9, 11:59 p.m. ET

Listening Session #2 conducted by DEI Task Force members:

Rosemary Ventura, DNP, RC-BC
Chief Nursing Informatics Officer
University of Rochester Medical Center

Harriet Burns, MD, MPH
Associate Medical Director for Informatics and Health Outcomes
Piedmont Health Services, Inc.

Why Are Listening Sessions Important?

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The session is designed to create a safe place for members to share as much detail as one feels comfortable sharing. **Anything disclosed during the sessions will be strictly confidential and comments will not be directly attributed to individuals.**

Sincerely,

Tiffani J. Bright, PhD, FACMI

tiffani.bright@gmail.com | [@doc_b_right](https://twitter.com/doc_b_right)

Chair, AMIA DEI Task Force

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This message was intended for: tiffani.bright@ibm.com

You were added to the system March 23, 2020.

For more information [click here](#). [Update your preferences](#)

[Unsubscribe](#) | [Unsubscribe via email](#)

Listening Sessions

AMIA Diversity, Equity and Inclusion Task Force

Focus Group:
Black and African-American

February 24th, 2021

Introduction & Welcome

Today's Facilitators

David K. Butler, MD FAMIA

Hope Gray, MTS, RBC

(Doctoral Candidate - UAB)

A 1-Minute Primer – ZOOM

- Use the **Raise Hand** feature for commenting verbally
- Use the **Chat feature** to send a direct message to to “**Host Only**” for privacy
- Use the Chat feature “**Everyone Publicly**” to share your thoughts with the group

CONFIDENTIALITY

- We want to create a safe place for you to share as much detail as you feel comfortable during this session.
- Anything you tell us here is strictly confidential.
- An AMIA member will take notes during the session which will **not** be directly attributed to you.
- These notes will be read only by members of the Task Force and findings will be reported only in aggregate to the Board.
- We may use a de-identified quote at some future presentation.

Listening Session Objectives

LISTENING SESSION OBJECTIVES

- **Candid discussions** among selected AMIA members related to various Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (DEI) challenges and opportunities within AMIA and Informatics
- Collect **confidential and candid feedback** from AMIA members
- **Analyze** for themes and actionable items
- **Present the findings and recommendations** to AMIA's Executive Board

Housekeeping/Rules of The Road

Rules of Road

- Mutual Respect For All In The Room – Safe Place
- Silence Notifications on Phones and Computers to Limit Distractions
- Be sincere in your questions, comments, and feedback
- No ‘ad hominem’ attacks... ”we attack the process, not person”
- Stop **Dave** from talking too much 😊
- **Dave** and **Hope** will re-direct or determine **Parking Lot items**
- All **feedback is confidential** and will be redacted and or summarized to ensure your privacy

Agenda For Today

Topic	Facilitators	Time	Comments
Introductions, Agenda, Housekeeping, and Icebreaker	David/Hope	12:00-12:05 pm	What To Expect Today
Members Introduction (1 min each)	Hope	12:10-12:20pm	#SelfLove #DontBeShy #SuperHero
Discussion Questions			
Questions 1- 3 (15 mins)	Group	12:20-12:35pm	Dialogue and Discussion*
Questions 4-8 (15 mins)	Group	12:35-12:50pm	Dialogue and Discussion*
Wrap Up/Closing Rounds (10 mins)	Dr. Butler/Hope Gray	12:50-1:00pm	- Closing Remarks and Next Steps

****Use Zoom Chat to Private Message to Hope Gray any comments or thoughts that you may not want to share with 'Everyone'**

Ice breaker Video

Group

Mosquitos and MicroAgression

FOR PEOPLE WHO STILL DON'T THINK

Introduction (1 min/participant)

Name | Current Job/Education | Hometown | **and 1** of the below

- *Favorite Super Hero & Why (Can't be a real person or animal ...sorry 😊)*

OR

- *Favorite Band, Singer, Artist, or Streaming Show (past year only)*

DISCUSSION QUESTIONS

DAVE

Discussion Topics

Question 1

Share the following:

Your experiences when actions, policies, behaviors, or structures within informatics have *positively* impacted the Black/African American community or you as a Black/African American informatics professional.

CONVERSATION STARTER:

*****Think about experiences during academic, professional training, or industry settings***

Discussion Topics

Question 2

Share the following:

Your experiences when actions, policies, behaviors, or structures within informatics have *negatively* impacted the Black/African-American community or you as a Black/African-American informatics professional.

CONVERSATION STARTER:

*****Think about experiences during academic, professional training, or industry settings***

Discussion Topics

Question 3

Share the following:

What can you tell us about AMIAs DEI efforts?

What do you think about the AMIA DEI efforts ?

CONVERSATION STARTER:

*****What have you seen, heard, or participated in during your tenure as an AMIA member related to DEI Efforts***

Discussion Topics

Question 4

Share the following:

What are three ways in which AMIA could work towards racial justice and equity?

Discussion Topics

Question 5

Share the following:

What are **three ways** that would make the AMIA community a more welcoming environment for you professionally and personally?

CONVERSATION STARTER:

****There are no bad suggestions or comments.**

Think of how other companies, organizations or academic institutions have created a more welcoming environment for Black people and African-Americans

Discussion Topics

Question 6 – 7

Share the following:

What is the responsibility of AMIA to be a catalyst for change in promoting and sustaining a racially just organizations?

What are three important steps AMIA could take?

Discussion Topics

Question 8

Share the following:

What else do you think we should know?

Wrap Up (10 min)

Questions or Comments

David K. Butler, MD

david.k.butler@calyxpartners.com

Hope Gray MTS, RBC

hopegray@uab.edu

Krista Martin, VP AMIA

krista@amia.org

Listening Session

March 16th, 2021

AMIA Diversity, Equity and Inclusion Task Force

Focus Group:
Hispanic/Latinx

Agenda

Topic	Facilitators		Time
Introductions, Agenda and Housekeeping	Rosemary /Harriett	12:00-12:05 pm	What To Expect Today
Members Introduction (1 min each)	Rosemary	12:10-12:20pm	#SelfLove #DontBeShy
Discussion Questions			
Questions 1- 3 (15 min)	Group	12:20-12:35p	15 Min Discussion
Questions 4-8 (15 min)	Group	12:35-12:50pm	15 Min Discussion
Wrap Up/Closing Rounds	Rosemary/Harriett	12:50-1:00pm	- Closing Remarks and Next Steps

Introduction & Welcome

Today's Facilitators

Rosemary Ventura, DNP, RN-BC
Harriett Burns, MD, MPH

Housekeeping/Guiding Principles

CONFIDENTIALITY

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- We may use a de-identified quote at some future presentation.

Guiding Principles

- Mutual Respect For All In The Room – Safe Place
- Silence Notifications on Phones and Computers to Limit Distractions
- Be sincere in your questions, comments, and feedback
- No ‘ad hominem’ attacks... ”we attack the process, not person”
- Be honest in your responses
- All voices are important
- **Rosemary** and **Harriett** will re-direct or determine **Parking Lot items**
- All **feedback is confidential** and will be redacted and or summarized to ensure your privacy**

Listening Session Objectives

LISTENING SESSION OBJECTIVES

- Candid discussions among selected AMIA members related to various Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (DEI) challenges and opportunities within AMIA and Informatics
- Collect confidential and candid feedback from AMIA membership
- Analyze for themes and actionable items
- Present to findings to AMIA's Executive Board

Ice breaker

Group

Introduction (1 min/participant)

Name | Current Job/Education | Hometown | **and 1 of the below**

- *Favorite Super Hero & Why (Can't be a real person or animal ...sorry 😞)*

OR

- *Favorite Band, Singer, Artist, or Streaming Show (past year only)*

Mosquitos and MicroAgression

Discussion Topics

Question 1

Share the following:

Your experiences when actions, policies, behaviors, or structures within informatics have *positively* impacted the Hispanic/Latinx community or you as a Hispanic/Latinx American informatics professional.

CONVERSATION STARTER:

*****Think about experiences during academic, training, or industry settings***

Discussion Topics

Question 2

Share the following:

Your experiences when actions, policies, behaviors, or structures within informatics have *negatively* impacted the Hispanic/Latinx community or you as a Hispanic/Latinx -American informatics professional.

CONVERSATION STARTER:

*****Think about experiences during academic, training, or industry settings***

Discussion Topics

Question 3

Share the following:

What can you tell us about AMIAs DEI efforts?

What do you think about the AMIA DEI efforts ?

CONVERSATION STARTER:

*****What have you seen, heard, or participated in during your tenure as an AMIA member related to DEI Efforts***

Discussion Topics

Question 4

Share the following:

What are three ways in which AMIA could work towards racial justice and equity?

Discussion Topics

Question 5

Share the following:

What are **three ways** that would make the AMIA community a more welcoming environment for you professionally and personally?

CONVERSATION STARTER:

*****There are no silly, bad, or dumb suggestions here. Think of how other companies, organizations or academic institutions have created a more welcoming environment for Hispanic/Latinx***

Discussion Topics

Question 6

Share the following:

What is the responsibility of AMIA to be a catalyst for change in promoting and sustaining a racially just organizations?

What are three important steps AMIA can take?

Wrap Up

- Check your emails and fill out a brief survey of the Listening Session
 - What could we have done different?
 - What did you enjoy?
 - Was this a meaningful use of your time

Table 1. Listening Session (LS) Findings

Question	LS	Response
1. Your experiences when actions, policies, behaviors, or structures within informatics have positively impacted the [Black or African American] [Hispanic/Latinx] community or you as a [Black or African American] [Hispanic/Latinx] informatics professional.	LS #1	1. I think the announcement that NAME was starting this the DEI efforts was a good step forward for the Black and African American communities.
		2. There is a program set up called AMIA First Look, which really brings in young African American women; really focusing on getting some of those who go to HBCUs; going to some of those schools that are not traditionally looked at, to bring them into AMIA to view it. And so I think that is a positive impact on the black community, we see several [students], continue to do things in informatics, continue to grow the program, we've seen them continue to present at other AMIA conferences too.
		3. Research by Timnit Gebru formerly of Google showed that facial recognition software misidentifies African Americans so the positive impact is that policies can be changed in police departments nationwide help decrease misidentification of Black people. Some police departments stopped using the technology. It helps if we are in this space to help make these changes.
		4. The AMIA workgroup, on interactive systems and in health, and the theme was focused on digital health equity, positively impacted me. Having more workgroups and symposiums, more sessions focused on health equity, and actually hearing from people who are doing the work within underserved communities and how the populations can be better served by considering their preferences and their needs.
		5. Glad to hear all of us share. Focus on Health Equity and actions from different companies and organization. Recently, the omnibus... I came across conversations around maternal health that specifically targeted the Black community and ensuring equity there.
		6. I'm very happy about collecting race and ethnicity data at the right point. I am advocating for this.
		7. Pipeline: Having AMIA members introduce Black students and professionals to the organization.
	LS #2	P1 had to start off the group because people thrown off by word "positively"
		1. Mentioned that at Brigham non-white, especially women were not in leadership – lots of efforts going on, but she has not seen concrete outcomes that have really helped
		2. Similar experience in AMIA that glad for efforts, but hasn't really experienced a benefit from it
		a. Women in AMIA, Networking, Professional Development
		3. Actual informatics itself is color blind, but it's the application of the principles when you bring value to the process; he feels he's been able to bring that knowledge to the community
		a. To reach out to communities to gather data – different perspective on how to reach out has made a difference and positive
		4. More brown and Black people hospitalized due to COVID
		5. 6 years ago ipad study with interpreters which is how he got looped into COVID projects
6. He recognized the digital divide – double edged source, new people are on the bandwagon		
7. Spanish patient portal now at Brigham – people leading these efforts always had the power and finally now taking action because of increased awareness		

	<p>8. The recognition that you must make more of an effort to reach out to the community and there are problems when...</p> <p>Response via email: My perception is that in general (in the US) there is a dearth of actions, policies, behaviors, or structures with a positive impact on the LatinX population and informatics community. Not only the Latinx informatics community is small but there is also a substantial gap of policies or initiatives to increase the number and active participation of students and professionals of this community in medical, health and healthcare informatics. The COVID-19 pandemic has triggered a higher level of awareness about the poor representation and inclusion of race/ethnic and other minorities in medical, health and healthcare informatics communities, academic institutions, and professional societies. The informatics professional societies and academic institutions have started discussions about addressing bias and lack of sociodemographic representation when developing algorithms, clinical decision support tools, and AI applied to health and healthcare. These are important first steps that will benefit the Latinx community and other minorities in the US. The hope is that these types of initiatives will increase the number and enhance the participation of members of the LatinX community in medical, health and healthcare informatics as well. Considering that Latinx-Americans represent the largest racial/ethnic minority group in the US, it is a priority to increase the number and active participation of students, professionals, researchers, and leaders of this community in careers in medical, health and healthcare informatics.</p>
<p>2. Your experiences when actions, policies, behaviors, or structures within informatics have negatively impacted the [Black or African American] [Hispanic/Latinx] community or you as a [Black or African American] [Hispanic/Latinx] informatics professional.</p>	<p>LS #1</p> <p>1. So again, as a newbie entering this area, one of the things that I became aware of is that we are using artificial intelligence, we're using datasets that don't include us. So when they don't include us, they are biased at the beginning. And so if we are not using our voice to make sure that we are included and that we are making sure that we are included in the information that tech technology companies are basing their stuff on, then it will always be biased towards us.</p> <p>2. Some of our predictive models, especially our predictive models for COVID-19, which all of us should know a little bit about. In some of the data, there was implicit bias. And when you look at the modeling, you can't put that in there. It's probably just the wrong conclusion. And then we get the wrong interventions, as a result we advocate for the wrong things.</p> <p>3. Even like, I think we saw things around pulse oximetry, right? The pulse oximetry, right, and the skin, it shows inaccuracy. In African Americans, there was a lot of things like that to go on to so I'm gonna shut up.</p> <p>4. Identifying who the informatics leaders who, you know, recognition of informatics leaders who are more inclusive and include more of African Americans. There was also reports around you know, some states not actually collecting data on race and ethnicity kind of going a little bit towards even as it relates to COVID. Implicit bias in data collection, and we can talk about that all day, all day every day.</p> <p>LS #2</p> <p>Not answered</p>
<p>3. What, if anything, can you tell us about the AMIA DEI efforts?</p>	<p>LS #1</p> <p>1. And there was a point where I actually stopped becoming a member because I didn't feel like there was anyone out there that was like me, a lot of information was definitely towards like more of the more of the scientific, theoretical, the type that really had no applicability to actually real life and so I just didn't feel like I fit and then be a person of color, especially back then I was usually the only one in the room.</p>

<p>What do you think about the AMIA DEI efforts?</p>	<p>2. Since, Patti Dykes has been in leadership, there has been more inclusivity. Dr. Dyke’s role has led to more reinforcement. Patti is a nurse, so that makes a difference and it’s a big deal. She is open to these concepts of trying to be more inclusive vs. the way it was in the past.</p> <p>3. It was definitely a white man club. And if you weren't an MD forget it. Right. So, it's like you had to be a white MD male kind of thing. And that's the way that was kind of the frame. That was to me that that was like the carbon copy. But I do think that Dr. Dykes being in her role has definitely led to some of these changes and the enforcement of it.</p> <p>4. The feedback has been very positive on the distance session. So, kudos to Tiffani and everyone, Tiffani has been there for a while. And she's been a leader and supporting her, supporting her voice, as well. I felt like I need to be here to support her.</p> <p>5. Yeah, I will also just like to add that I'm very new to the AI space, I think some of the things that we've talked about is just larger systems. Like I'm the only black woman in my cohort, like probably in the department at XYZ University in terms of being in this field. Also, I want to study Bioinformatics, like, I think that the clinical application is great, but I'm really interested in like metabolites and lipids and pathways and all of those things. And I don't ever feel like I know who to talk to, if there's just anyone, like in this space that I can talk to like, going to the AMIA website. It's not like on the first page, like I would really have to go and find and search the website to try to find something about the AI and like what the organization is doing. I think it would be nice. So I wrote everyone's name down. So I can connect with you all on LinkedIn. But just to know people who are like in this space, like, I think that's the thing is, I just don't know who's in this space, who's doing what I'm doing. It's always good to see black women who are successful, and the role is your cycle. What did you do? How did you get there? How did you deal with just all the microaggressions I've just all of them and just you know, Wendy, when do you educate someone about it? When do you not educate someone about it and just, you know, just I would look more for support and who I could turn to, and I think this is a very good step. I just don't think it's public. It's not on the website when you first go on there. I think that's something that should change.</p>
	<p>LS #2</p> <p>1. People not aware of DEI task force until this recent outreach</p> <p>2. P1 mentions AMIA only recently started to collect race/ethnicity information of their members</p> <p>Response via email: I am aware in general terms about the DEI Task Force goals but I honestly don't know and I am not aware about ongoing specific initiatives, projects, and activities that are considered priorities by the DEI Task Force. All the goals of the DEI Task Force represent priorities to increase the number and participation of race/ethnic and other minority groups within AMIA and externally. The DEI needs to have a stronger presence within AMIA and activities such as the current feedback session are important first steps to increase the number and participation of Latinx informaticians in health and healthcare.</p>
<p>4. What are three ways in which AMIA could work towards racial</p>	<p>LS #1</p> <p>1. Internships, mentors, more pathways, more access. Not being able to get your foot in the door.</p> <p>2. Self-nomination to be on the board is important vs the way it was Not fair that other doctors are “grandfathered” into being Clinical Informaticists</p> <p>3. What about people who are not MDs who are qualified as clinical informaticist and have years of experience</p>

justice and equity?		4. I'm a licensed doctor in another country. But, I'm not qualified here to become a Clinical Informaticist
		5. Put more people at the table. It can't always be the ones coming from Harvard. How gets accepted. The Clinical Informaticist have been white males. Where are the women
		6. Show the inequity in under-represented minorities in our membership. See paper in JAMIA about people coming into Bioinformatics field. Have a dashboard on AMIA site to display the disparity so we are more vigilant to bring in more diversity.
		7. Bring all inclusion onto the Board. The current criteria will continue the pattern of White males and females. Maybe through the governance committee.
		8. View systemically, when DEI is not at the foundation it cannot be the icing. DEI needs to be included in the mission and vision for AMIA. Start at the root. What are the strategic objectives? Incorporate DEI, every step of the way. To get to K-12, HBCUs that would be branches or fruit that would come from this exercise.
		Additional Comments from those that had to depart at the full hour. • How inclusive are the governance policies? Hopeful that updates will be made. • DEI environmental scan has been done recently. Multipronged approach. Need DEI officer, Taskforce (people who are paid to do this work). Unless they feel there is a need for racial justice, they don't see the benefit to AMIA, healthcare in general. Otherwise, they'll continue the same pipeline
	LS #2	1. Outreach program structured around getting people into the field, and keeping tabs on number of recruits that come from underserved
		2. He has seen success from Women in AMIA – could you clone that program to achieve success
		3. AMIA could use its platform and its voice to raise awareness, inform members, reach out to more communities
5. What are three ways that would make the AMIA community a more welcoming environment for you professionally and personally?	LS #1	Not answered
	LS #2	1. More advertisement and resources to alert people that what groups are available
		2. Not only through invitations but other resources (like what "X" was mentioning that she doesn't know how to participate successfully in AMIA)
		3. Important to differentiate the work of AMIA vs. IMIA
		4. Scheduling of different activities; important to highlight the work that comes out of
		5. Cycle of IMIA is slower
		6. Being in AMIA is very expensive – differential membership to increase inclusion
		a. Cost
	b. We are propagating the digital divide – e.g., the benefits of telehealth went to privileged one	
	c. We also cannot forget about other languages of Latin America as well	
		7. Unintentional harm of pushing more technology that may be exacerbating health disparities if we are not careful

		8. Idea for having Blue Ribbon panel to look at unanticipated, adverse consequences due to increased use of technology in healthcare	
		a. How to do it right	
		9. AI algorithms need to be inclusive while being supportive to our African American	
		10. We also don't want to simplify what it means to be Latinx – points to the diversity of this group	
		11. Emphasized the importance of increasing translational and cultural in addition to intellectual and academic	
		12. We paid the minority tax vs. taking the white subsidy	
		13. What are the concrete measures of success – putting informaticist hat on to say we need to put hard work in to develop these measures	
		Response via email: 1. Increasing opportunities for research, policy work, leadership positions, volunteer work, etc. directed to members of racial and ethnic minorities;	
		2. Providing leadership training opportunities to ethnic/racial and other minority members of AMIA;	
		2. Encouraging members of ethnic/racial and other minority groups to take leadership roles within AMIA	
6. What is the responsibility of AMIA to be a catalyst for change in promoting and sustaining a racially just organizations? What are three important steps AMIA could take?	LS #1	1. Continue to recognize that racial justice and equality are an issue in informatics.	
		2. Question: What is AMIA's relationship with other diverse organizations?	
		1. As a physician, I wasn't aware that this organization existed. I could have learned about this if there was a partnership	
		2. Trans community	
		3. Black Girls Code	
		3. We are supposed to look like the field of who we server. We should be looking to get more people into the field that are diverse. What are the organizations that represent the marginalized population?	
		4. Yes, partner with other organizations. We are missing the power of youth. Think of the youth who don't go into science because they've had a negative experience. I didn't learn about informatics until I was going through my second masters. I didn't want to be in the lab. I wanted to do DNA sequencing. AMIA could be a catalyst. My school did a partnership with Verizon. They provided funding and materials to learn about informatics. Look at community colleges not just 4-year colleges. Show people how they can be involved in this space. You don't have to be a doctor or an engineer.	
		5. Pipeline Committee with Women in AMIA – we are looking to going into schools. But we need AMIA to promote and support the working groups initiatives. Assess what is going on within the workgroups that are DEI initiatives.	
		6. Women In AMIA podcast – more people support this effort. It's not just for women. One person learned about Tiffani Bright through the podcast.	
		Establish a Monthly or Quarterly Meetup for each affinity groups.	
		LS #2	1. AMIA may need to be more thoughtful about how to affect change in communities (less academic and more translational)
			2. AMIA could help by affecting policy about needed data standards
			a. Example about health center in New Orleans collecting only Black, White, and Other when there is a very large Honduran population

3. More people publishing now that they know it's a popular
4. Spoke about population in TX 27% and half of that population not speaking English
5. Simple things about use of cogger in S. America vs. in Mexico
6. AMIA Annual Symposium – appreciated having some space to connect to others working in Latin America
7. Latin America is very diverse – creating more spaces to meet and have experiences together
8. Different focus between 1st generation and 2nd generation; AMIA should take that into account, outreach to countries vs. outreach to 2nd generation Latinos in US
9. Wants to see AMIA encourage more young people to get interested in the profession
10. He is disappointed that high school students underrepresented minorities are actively discouraged to go into sciences
11. Wants to see AMIA be more active in those forums to address this; he sees other organizations that are more involved
12. AMIA is very influential with NLM so can there be more programs to recruit young people into the profession – X says it should go down to kindergarten, also Y
13. Only in AMIA x 1 month, got a lot of emails, but still not sure she
14. Partner/mentor to help others get involved in AMIA
15. More international efforts

Response via email: In order for AMIA to become a catalyst organization promoting health equity, social justice in healthcare, and broad and effective inclusion of racial/ethnic and other minority groups in medical informatics and computer science, it first needs to achieve these goals or milestones INTERNALLY (start in-house!). Before AMIA can become a leader professional organization promoting racial justice in society, it needs to become more inclusive and diverse, as well as provide clearly and unequivocally opportunities for career development for members of racial/ethnic and other minorities with particular emphasis and attention to younger and new AMIA members. We need more members of racial/ethnic and other minorities actively working in leadership positions, steering committees, research projects, policy change initiatives, etc. 1. Partner with academic institutions and schools located or serving predominantly racial/ethnic and other minorities to develop outreach programs encouraging membership in AMIA 2. Develop AMIA-sponsored informatics/computer science early-career development programs for college and high school graduates from racial/ethnic and other minority groups. The programs can be diverse and include research, health policy initiatives, public health activities, etc. 3. Increase AMIA's presence and encourage membership in the organization among the healthcare workforce of medically underserved and rural areas. Membership rates for healthcare professionals of medically underserved and rural areas would have a discounted rate and added benefits such as lower rates for participation in AMIA-sponsored conferences. Moreover, membership rates for nurses, dietitians, physical therapists, respiratory therapists, social workers, nurses practitioners, etc. would be lower as compared to those for physicians.

LS #1 "Refined inclusion criteria on the AMIA Board"

General comments via chat	<p>"Development of k-12 educational resources. Developing curriculum and programs to invest students at an early age. Development of pathways early in their life. Provide support/curriculum/funding/experiences for students to enter in the field."</p> <p>"Changing the narrative at the core, DEI is not against white, it is against white-only."</p> <p>"Inclusion is excellence. Pleasure meeting you all and hope to connect within and outside AMIA. Best regards. have a nice rest of day!"</p> <p>"It was good to virtually meet all of you. Let's all keep in touch. This was great!!! Thank you so very much."</p> <p>"A mentor match programs across orgs that may partner with AMIA."</p> <p>"Thanks for this opportunity to share thoughts. I have to log off."</p> <p>"Thank you all for being leaders in these efforts!"</p>
LS #2	<p>"I always say that if we do not have representation in the front end at the table it will not translate on the back end to contribute to various populations."</p> <p>"We need to strengthen and make it visible or mentorship mechanism. And target it to Latinx."</p> <p>"Totally agree with what has been said. I would add that it is also important to bring awareness to AMIA community in terms of inherent bias when it comes to grouping Latinx all together. It is important to highlight the genetic, biological, cultural differences when it comes to Latinx being the recipients of informatics applications in the context of medicine and healthcare."</p> <p>"1. They need broader representation at the senior level. 2. Then need to do a broader connection through the pipeline as we mentioned. 3. We have to also ensure policies to properly know what the current landscape is with limited data and bias and create a framework and plan for the future that are inclusive and have appropriate structure. I think there are also needs a broader international connection vs local under-represented connection and that these are buckets with intersection. While I also think initiatives start with Diversity, I hope that Equity and Inclusion are also an integral part."</p>